

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF KIDNEY BEAN/WHEAT FLOUR BLENDS.

Okoye J.I¹, Nkwocha A.C¹ and Agbo A.O².

¹Department of Food Science and Technology, Madonna University, Elele Campus, P.M.B 48, Elele, Rivers State, Nigeria. ²Department of Industrial Chemistry, Elele Campus, P.M.B 48, Elele, Rivers State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The chemical and functional characteristics of kidney bean and wheat flour blends were examined. The kidney bean flour (KF) was composite with wheat flour (WF) at the levels of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%. The flour blends were analysed for their chemical composition and functional characteristics. From the results, the protein content of the blends increased with increasing supplementation with kidney bean flour from 22.74% in 50:50 (KF:WF) to 27.24% in 90:10 (KF:WF) samples, while the carbohydrate decreased. Contrarily, the energy content of the blends increased gradually as the level of fortification with kidney bean flour decreased from 360.60KJ in 90:10 (KF:WF) to 362.15KJ in 50:50 (KF:WF). The results also showed that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in emulsion capacity, and oil and water absorption capacities of the blends.

KEYWORDS: Chemical, functional, characteristics, kidney bean-wheat flour mixtures.

INTRODUCTION

In most developing countries of the world including Nigeria, where diets are composed mainly of one plant staple food, the occurrence of protein-energy malnutrition especially among children is common. As the cost of producing meat, milk, egg and fish which are foods of high biological values increase, plant proteins offer ready and affordable solution to the problem of a growing protein gap.

Low cost, protein-rich and high energy food formulation based on cereal legume mixtures have been suggested (Akobundu and Hoskins, 1987); Marero *et al.*, 1988; Okaka *et al.*, 1992). The enrichment or fortification of traditional cereal based diets with other protein sources such as oilseeds and legumes has received considerable attention. This is because oil seed and legumes proteins are rich in lysine, but deficient in sulphur containing amino acids (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Legumes generally contain relatively high amount of protein than other plant food stuffs. Cereals have a low protein content and are in general deficient in lysine but are adequate in sulphur containing amino acids. Legume proteins are mainly used in food formulations to complement the protein in cereal grains because of their chemical and nutritional characteristics (Enwere, 1998).

Kidney bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) a grain legume, is one of the neglected tropical legumes that can be used to fortify cereal-based diets especially in developing countries, because of its high protein content (Akobundu *et al.*, 1992). It is also a rich source of vitamin, minerals and relatively high in crude fibre (NAS, 1979). Kidney bean is one such protein source, which when used in the fortification or enrichment of cereal – based diets could go a long way in improving their nutritional status. The objective of study was to examine the chemical and functional properties of kidney bean-wheat flour blends.

Fig 1: Flow chart for the production of cooked kidney bean flour.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mature kidney bean seeds (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) and the wheat flour used for this study were bought from local market in Owerri, Nigeria. This research work was carried out in the Department of Food Science and Technology, Madonna University, Elele, River State, Nigeria in November, 2007.

Table 1: Flour Blends

Samples	KF (%)	WF (%)
A	90	10
B	80	20
C	70	30
D	60	40
E	50	50

KF = Kidney bean flour; WF = wheat flour

Table 2: Means^{1,2} of Proximate Composition of Kidney bean/Wheat flour blends on dry weight basis.

Samples	Moisture (%)	Nx5.75 protein (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	Fibre (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Energy (KJ/100g)
A	13.32 ^a	27.24 ^a	2.36 ^a	4.12 ^a	4.56 ^a	57.60 ^a	360.60 ^a
B	12.12 ^b	27.13 ^b	2.48 ^a	4.08 ^a	4.52 ^a	57.45 ^a	360.64 ^a
C	9.03 ^c	26.25 ^c	3.05 ^b	3.98 ^b	3.22 ^b	57.70 ^a	361.64 ^a
D	8.86 ^d	23.63 ^d	3.45 ^c	1.66 ^c	2.24 ^c	59.14 ^b	362.13 ^b
E	8.68 ^c	22.74 ^c	4.15 ^d	1.33 ^d	1.82 ^d	58.57 ^c	362.15 ^b

1. Values are means of triplicates samples
2. Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$).

Preparation of Kidney bean flour

The kidney bean flour was prepared according to the method described by Giami and Bekebain (1992) as shown in Figure 1. During preparation, two kilograms of kidney bean seeds which were free from dirt and other foreign materials such as stones, sticks and leaves were weighed, cleaned and soaked in tap water for 6 hours. After soaking, the seeds were drained, dehulled manually, boiled (100°C, 30mins) and dried in the cabinet dryer (65°C, 6h). During drying, the dehulled seeds were stirred at intervals of 30 minutes to ensure uniform drying. The dried seeds were milled (attrition mill) and sieved to pass through a 300 mesh sieve. The cooked kidney bean flour obtained was finally packaged in sealed polyethylene bags due to the hygroscopic nature of the flour until used for blending and analysis.

Flour Blending

The kidney bean flour (KF) was composite with wheat flour (WF) at the levels of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% in a kenwood mixer (Model A 990). There after, the flour blends were individually packaged in sealed polyethylene bags and kept at room temperature until used for analysis. The various flour blends produced are shown in Table 1.

Chemical Analysis

The moisture, protein, fat, ash and fibre contents of each of the flour blends were determined in triplicates using the methods of AOAC (1990). The carbohydrate was determined by difference (Iherokoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). The food energy was calculated using the Atwater factor 4 x protein, 4 x carbohydrate, 9 x fat (Bryant *et al.*, 1988).

Evaluation of Functional Properties

Emulsion capacity, water and oil absorption capacities and bulk density of each of the flour blends were determined in triplicates by the methods of Okezie and Bello (1988). Swelling capacity was determined according to the method of AOAC (1990).

Statistical Analysis

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on all the data after the analyses to detect significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the sample values. The turkey test was used in separating significant means.

Table 3: Means^{1,2} of functional properties of Kidney bean/wheat flour blends on dry weight basis.

Samples	Emulsion capacity (ml/g)	Oil absorption capacity (ml/g)	Water absorption capacity (ml/g)	Bulk density (g/ml)	Swelling capacity (%)
A	9.62 ^a	6.28 ^a	9.48 ^a	0.98 ^a	257.1 ^a
B	9.54 ^b	6.26 ^a	9.4a ^a	0.96 ^a	256.2 ^a
C	9.42 ^c	5.86 ^b	9.36 ^b	0.97 ^a	255.6 ^a
D	9.30 ^d	5.62 ^b	9.24 ^c	0.94 ^a	256.6 ^a
E	9.22 ^c	4.48 ^c	9.16 ^d	0.96 ^a	256.4 ^a

1. Values are means of triplicates samples
2. Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate composition of the flour blends are shown in Table 2. The moisture contents of the blends ranged from 8.68% to 13.32%. The differences could be attributed to inadequate drying of kidney bean seeds after soaking and boiling. The protein content of all the flour blends differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) from each other. The differences were observed because the protein content of the blends increased steadily with increasing content of kidney bean flour (KF). However, kidney beans have been reported to be good sources of protein (Duke, 1981). This addition effect was also observed for ash and fibre. In other words, the ash, fibre and protein contents of the blends increased as the level of kidney flour inclusion increased. However, the opposite effect (subtraction effect) was observed for fat and carbohydrate contents of the flour blends. The results of fat and carbohydrate contents of the blends are generally in agreement with those reported by Akpapunam and Darbe (1994). The energy contents of the blends ranged from 360.60KJ/100g to 362.15KJ/100g. The energy content of the flour blends was generally higher than those reported by Giami *et al.*, (2000).

The increase in the energy content of the blends resulted from their high protein and carbohydrate contents. The supplementation of wheat flour (WF) with kidney bean flour (KF) produced the desired effect of increasing the protein content of the blends, which will invariably improve the nutritional quality of the products made from these flour blends.

The results of the functional properties of the blends are shown in Table 3. From the results, the emulsion capacity of the blends ranged from 9.22ml/g to 9.62ml/g with samples A and B having the highest values. The variations in emulsion capacity of the blends could be attributed to differences in their globular protein contents (Sathe *et al.*, 1982). Flour with good emulsion capacities will be useful in the preparation of comminuted meat products and analogs. The oil absorption capacity of the blends differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) from each other. They were also higher than those reported by Akubor *et al.*, (2000). However, flours with high oil absorption capacities will perform excellently as meat extenders. The water absorption capacity of the flour blends ranged from 9.16ml/g. The differences could be attributed to the milling process subjected to each of the flour during processing which resulted in starch damage (Wolf, 1970). The high water absorption capacities of the blends will make them useful in the formulation of doughnuts and pancakes. The bulk density of the blends was generally higher than those previously reported for flour and

was also not significantly different from each other ($p>0.05$). The increase in the bulk density of the blends could be due to the cooking treatment adopted during the processing of kidney bean flour (Arkroyed and Doughty, 1982). The high bulk density of the blends will be an advantage in the formation of confectionery products. The swelling capacity of the blends ranged from (255.60% - 257.10) %

The result also showed that there was no significant difference in the swelling capacity of the flour blends ($p>0.05$). The increase in the swelling capacity of the samples could be due to their high protein contents (Chang and Satter, 1981). The high swelling capacities of the blends will make them useful in the preparation of soups, puddings and sauces. However, the kidney bean/wheat blended flours could be used as protein supplement and as functional ingredients in the formulation of a number of food products.

CONCLUSION

The enhancement of the nutritional value of wheat and other cereal flours with the inclusion of kidney bean flour could help to alleviate the problem of malnutrition prevalent in rural areas of our society. From the findings of this study, it was observed that the fortification of wheat and other cereal flours with kidney bean flour at a level up 50% would help immensely in improving their nutritional value and functional characteristics. Further studies should be performed on the flour blends to determine their respective protein quality and amino acid composition.

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Corresponding Author:

Okoye J.I

Department of Food Science and Technology, Madonna University, Elele Campus, P.M.B 48, Elele, Rivers State, Nigeria.